

15.12.22: Communication and dissemination strategy

WP 8: Communication and Dissemination

Authors: UNIFR

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History of changes – 31.05.24

General updates:

- Names of people updated (p.8)
- General evaluation of social channels and particularly Facebook (p.15)

Indicators:

- Results added on the table of indicators (p.18)
- New table of indicators added for the second part of the project (p.36)

Evaluation

- Summary of the internal evaluations added (p.27)

Table of contents

Document information	2
Document history	2
Disclaimer.....	2
History of changes – 31.05.24	3
Executive summary	5
II. Communication and dissemination framework	6
2.1 Obligations for dissemination and open access.....	6
2.2 Visibility	6
2.3 Roles and responsibilities of partners.....	7
2.4 Key principles	9
III. Dissemination strategy.....	9
3.1 Overall objectives.....	9
3.2 Two pathways	10
3.3 Target audiences	10
3.4 Channels by target audience.....	14
IV. Activities and monitoring	15
4.1 Three overall tasks	15
4.2 General timeline.....	16
4.3 Activities and key indicators	17

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4.4	Steps to update the strategy.....	26
4.5	Summary of the result of the internal and overall evaluation	26
V.	Communication toolbox.....	27
5.1	Logo.....	28
5.2	Fonts.....	29
5.3	Colours	30
5.4	Website	30
5.5	Social media	31
5.6	Templates.....	31
a.	Project leaflet.....	31
b.	Covers for social media platforms	31
c.	PowerPoint presentations	32
d.	LEGITIMULT official deliverable template	33
e.	Working and policy papers	34
f.	Newsletter	34
5.7	Content of the shared drive.....	34
VI.	Update of the indicators – May 2024 to September 2025	35

Table of figures

Figure 1: Communication objectives	10
Figure 2: Summary of the strategy and tasks	16
Figure 3: Compact versions of the logo	28
Figure 4: Extended versions of the logo	29
Figure 5: Menu layout.....	31
Figure 6: Profile picture	32
Figure 7: Banner for social media	32
Figure 8: LEGITIMULT deliverable template (cover).....	33
Figure 9: Content of the common drive.....	34

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Executive summary

LEGITIMULT explores measures taken to manage and mitigate the Covid-19 pandemic. In particular, the project examines decisions taken, measures implemented, and processes followed that impacted on democratic governance through the perspective of multilevel governance (MLG). LEGITIMULT aims to develop a model of legitimate crisis governance that safeguards democratic standards and prevents social fragmentation and alienation. The project has three main objectives :

- (1) Assessing the impact of the Covid-19 measures on democratic governance;
- (2) Evaluating the impact of MLG institutions on Covid-19 measures and on the impact of these measures on MLG governance and wider questions of democratic legitimacy;
- (3) Improving the governance of future crises by interactively developing a toolbox on legitimate crisis governance and several learning tools to apply it.

LEGITIMULT's consortium includes ten partners in Europe and one in Canada. Some of the case studies of the project are located in Iceland, Norway, Switzerland and the United Kingdom – countries which are not members of the European Union.

Findings of the research will be widely shared between several audiences in order to develop and strengthen the discussion on the impact of crises on democratic governance. These findings are gathered in a set of policy recommendations, and merged into a toolkit for legitimate crisis governance, ready for use in possible future crises. This dissemination strategy aims to provide the tools to build, adapt, diffuse and participate in the implementation and use of this toolkit. It follows the structure of a funnel, starting from overall objectives to more precise actions. It also delivers indications for the strategy's further development and updates.

In the first part, a general framework for dissemination and communication is presented. In particular, it is aligned with the Open Science principles. Second, the framework is narrowed down to a more focused and anchored strategy. Actions and key indicators are then described in order to carry out the strategy. Finally, tools and instructions are provided for the implementation of the strategy among all partners of the LEGITIMULT consortium.

This strategy is the first deliverable of the Work Package 8 "Dissemination and Communication". It will be updated in Months 9, 15, 21 and 33 of the project to ensure an iterative and reflexive approach.

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I. Communication and dissemination framework

1.1 Obligations for dissemination and open access

According to Article 17.1 of the Grant Agreement, each partner of the LEGITIMULT project is obliged to promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a coherent and effective manner. Whenever the partners expect that a communication or dissemination activity will have a major media impact, they need to inform the European Commission as the granting authority via UNIFR and Eurac Research.

Annex 5 to the Grant Agreement provides more information: all partners have to disseminate the results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format (subject to restrictions due to protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests). Other partners may object to the dissemination of results within 15 days of **receiving notification via email**, if they can show that their legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. Then, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Dissemination activities will remain compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality and personal data protection obligations, and the legitimate interests of the owners of the results.

In general, as part of the full LEGITIMULT project, Work Package 8 “Dissemination and Communication” will also comply with the separately developed Ethics Plan and Data Management Plan, ensuring the compliance with all ethical standards and the open, safe and transparent management of data and results. UNIFR is in charge of Work Package 8.

1.2 Visibility

In line with Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement, all communication activities and the results related to the project (including electronic forms) must include both the EU emblem and a text indicating that the project has received funding from the EU.

Moreover, it must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor SERI can be held responsible for them.”

The University of Fribourg (UNIFR) in Switzerland, is part of the project as an associated partner. It has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). In line with article 4.8 of SERI’s contract with UNIFR, a specific mention also needs to be displayed alongside the one for the EU with the SERI’s logo.

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1.3 Roles and responsibilities of partners

All consortium members are expected to participate in the communication and dissemination activities to ensure the widest possible dissemination. The following tasks are therefore expected :

- Follow-up of the activities described in the [table of key activities and indicators](#) in order to work as multipliers for dissemination.
- Press follow-up of articles and mention of the project in the media of the partner's country: published articles must be sent to the communication manager of the Institute of Federalism, UNIFR. Articles and any media mention as well. They will be kept for the report of WP 8.
- Scientific monitoring of articles or news related to the project and sharing of this news with the communication manager of UNIFR for dissemination on the project's social networks.
- Liking and sharing of project news on social networks in case of relevance for the partners. A table with relevant social media handles will be available on the Teams Share Drive of the project.
- Feedback on proposed infographics and explanations of the project.
- Translation of the flyer (one page) presenting the project into the language(s) of the country (when feasible).

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1.4 Key principles

Several key principles frame LEGITIMULT's pathway to impact. These principles are to be strictly respected by all consortium partners when results or outputs are released to guarantee the quality of the dissemination:

- 1 **Ensure the quality of the results** through systematic peer review and sharing.
- 2 **Branding through** the graphic charter and visual identity of the project in order to always be identifiable by all types of **readers**.
- 3 **Adapt communication to the audience**. A work of translation and equivalence must systematically be carried out to simplify academic language for e.g.
- 4 Respect the audiences and in particular the **gender perspective**: provide a non-stereotyped image of women, a balanced representation of the sexes, the use of a non-sexist language and consider women as a specific target group.

II. Dissemination strategy

The dissemination and communication strategy is the foundation of all our communication work. It responds to overall objectives in lines with our key principles. These are divided into specific objectives and guide us to define our audience and channels to reach them.

2.1 Overall objectives

The dissemination and exploitation strategy has the following **four overall main objectives**:

1. Communicating the specific outputs and results (e.g. communication strategies) of the project to the predefined and continually identified target groups; raising awareness for the project among relevant decision-makers, the broad public and the scientific community. This objective includes a specific effort to communicate how our collaborative research is contributing to a European Innovation Union.
2. Involving decision-makers, other key stakeholders as well as the scientific community in the ongoing debate on the progress of the project, in order to generate additional input for the research and to ensure that results will be useful for innovative policy-making.
3. Serving as a database for other researchers, decision-makers, stakeholders, in teaching to ensure synergies with other projects, future use of results and follow-up by other projects.
4. Considering the gender perspective in our operational and communication activities. The research team is committed to providing a non-stereotyped image of women, a balanced representation of the sexes, the use of a non-sexist language as well as to considering women as a specific target group.

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Figure 1: Communication objectives

2.2 Two pathways

In order to reach the overall objectives, two specific pathways have been conceived:

- Providing and managing the instruments and processes, guaranteeing easy, open and trusted access of data and outputs for all interested parties (project partners, stakeholders and wider audience) while anchoring the project thoroughly in Europe’s Open Science Policy.
- Facilitating strong engagement with the practitioners’ community in public authorities as well as in academia and with ordinary citizens.

2.3 Target audiences

Identifying and targeting the appropriate audience is essential for an effective and relevant strategy. LEGITIMULT distinguishes three main target groups:

Policy-makers from global: European, national and subnational levels
Citizens
Scientific community: research practitioners and researchers/research institutions

The project applies decentralized strategy that considers the specifics of each team/country and that builds on regional contacts and networks of all partners. It is essential and functional to better understand their needs, methods of communication, and related characteristics.

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Table 1: Detailed target audiences (threefold)

POLICY-MAKERS FROM GLOBAL, EUROPEAN, NATIONAL AND SUBNATIONAL LEVELS		
Target groups	Interest in LEGITIMULT project	Objectives for this target
Executive leaders at the global level: WHO leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information of the project's impact at all levels of government - Development of more accurate and legitimate recommendations for crisis governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness on the project and its results through policy briefs and working papers
Executive leaders at the European level: EU: members of the European Commission, European Parliament, European Committee of the Regions, Council of Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More precise calculation of risks for democracy - Detailed evaluations of European policies and their impact - Development of synergies at the European level - Development of tools for EU states in order to strengthen their legitimate crisis management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of the project and its results through policy briefs and working papers - Active participation of key stakeholders during conferences and workshops
Executive leaders at the national and regional level: leaders from health ministries at the federal level in Southern, Eastern, Western and Northern Europe¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate policies of crisis management - Access to data concerning the crisis governance of other countries - Support more legitimate policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active participation of key stakeholders in the design of e-learning courses - Active participation of key stakeholder during our mid-term and final conferences - Diffusion and promotion of the <i>Toolkit on legitimate crisis governance</i>
High-level civil servants from health ministries or health departments/administration at the local level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compare their action to others - Be more prepared for crises to come 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage through participation in our e-learning courses - Knowledge on the <i>Toolkit on legitimate crisis governance</i> - Direct engagement and participation in a two-week full time in-person practitioners' seminar

¹ As defined by the UN Geoscheme for Europe: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/external/un-geoscheme-standard-m49>.

CITIZENS		
Target groups	Interest in LEGITIMULT project	Objectives for this target
Media and institutional communication experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information for a broader public on a scientific project - Tools for public discussion of policies - Relevant findings to understand the impact of crises on the sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness on the project and its results through policy briefs and working papers and participation in a one-day workshop - Promotion and diffusion of key findings through news - Translation of key findings to a more general audience connecting science, policy, and the broader public
Civil society: NGOs involved in crisis governance monitoring like Amnesty International, Transparency International, Swiss Peace, ..., and local associations (still to define)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate policies of crisis management - Tools for public discussion of policies— More precise calculation of risks for democracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness on the project and its results through policy briefs and working papers and participation in a one-day workshop - Active participation of key stakeholders in the design of our e-learning course - Diffusion and promotion of the <i>Toolkit on legitimate crisis governance</i>
“Citizen juries” of citizens of various ages, gender, social classes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluate policies toward crisis management - Concern about the effects of these policies on the daily life of citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of the project and its results through media - Participation in citizen juries

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SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY, RESEARCH PRACTITIONERS AND RESEARCHERS/RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS		
Target groups	Interest in LEGITIMULT project	Objectives for this target
Experts: members of the various task forces and persons who advised the ministries during the Covid-19 crisis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete and strengthen knowledge of crisis governance - More analysis and understanding on the effects of policies to provide appropriate and respectful advice on democracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of the project and its results through policy briefs, working papers and literature review - Active participation of key stakeholders during conferences - Direct engagement through participation in our e-learning course - Knowledge on the <i>Toolkit on legitimate crisis governance</i>
Scientific community from various fields beyond the consortium members: political science, public administration, constitutional law, sociology, crisis governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information on a methodological framework: quantitative and qualitative methods - Information on a new scientific framework: legitimate crisis governance - Findings to fill gap in knowledge through a dataset on MLG impact on Covid-19 measures - Discussion and critique to consolidate findings and build new research projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness of the project and its results through Open Science and Open Access peer-reviewed journal articles and the datasets developed during the project - Review of the books and articles written by researchers of the project - Active discussions on the findings during conferences - Circulation and citations of LEGITIMULT's results
Think tanks, foundations and private research institutes (such as the Center for Security Studies in Zürich, IRIS in France, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scientific contributions to build further research - Access to spaces of exchange and discussion - Further advancement and research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness and use of policy briefs and working papers - Citations of LEGITIMULT's results

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2.4 Channels by target audience

Each target group needs to have a tailored approach and there are various channels to reach them. Some channels may overlap, but many are target group-specific. In order to deliver customized messages, meeting the interests of the different targets, LEGITIMULT will make use of optimal channels as described below in Table 2.

Table 2: Engagement and use of communication channels by target audiences (estimations)

Engagement and use of communication channels by target audiences	Policy-makers from global, European, national and subnational levels	Citizens	Scientific community, research practitioners and researchers/research institutions
Facebook	Low engagement/use:	Medium	Low
X (formerly Twitter)	Medium	Medium	High
LinkedIn	High	Medium	High
LEGITIMULT website	High	Low	High
Media	High	High	Medium
Conferences and workshops	High	Low	High
E-learning course	High	Low	High
Books and peer-reviewed articles	Low	Low	High
Citizen juries	Low	High	Low
Policy briefs	High	Low	Medium
Working papers	High	Low	High
In-person and informal meetings	High	Low	Medium
Newsletter	Medium	Low	Medium

Update May 2024: Facebook use has been very low for all our targets. In Europe, it seems not to be used that much anymore for research projects, whereas it remains very much used in other areas. We will nonetheless keep our Facebook account alive, as it is still the main social media platform used by adults in Europe². We will use it more specifically to disseminate information about the citizens juries to come.

² <https://comarketing-news.fr/quels-sont-les-reseaux-sociaux-les-plus-utilises-par-les-europeens/>

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III. Activities and monitoring

Our strategy will be implemented through three tasks. Several activities will be carried out under each of them according to specific timelines. Monitoring will be assured by the follow-up of core indicators and steps to update the strategy and its implementation.

3.1 Three overall tasks

Our three tasks for communication and dissemination are the following ones: (1) outreach and network-communication with institutional partners functioning as multipliers, (2) print and online publishing of the consortium partners' activities as well as all scientific and para-scientific communication, and (3) the project's durable web-platform as a showcase and database for research activities, results and outputs, in addition to trusted repositories for publications and data.

T8.1 Outreach and involvement of partners functioning as multipliers

First, the dissemination is supported by a multiplier approach. Each of the four consortium partners involved in work package 8 (UNIFR, Eurac, IDEA, ForFed) has a substantial network of practitioners, politicians, and senior officials. From these four "network heads", other key structures will be reached out such as the Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe, the EU's European Committee of the Regions, the Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe, the Council of European Municipalities and Regions, Eurocities, the EU Neighbours programme, and the EU's Interreg cooperation-programme, but also to specialised committees of the WHO and of the WHO Regional Office for Europe.

In addition to these network heads, each partner also has its own links and contacts, as well as its own channels of communication and distribution. The project and its communication channels will serve as a sort of database from which everyone can draw information to feed the dissemination.

Each partner and each communication channel will thus be a multiplier to approach our target audiences.

T8.2 Printing and online publishing of the consortium partners' activities, as well as other communication instruments

The second pillar of dissemination-efforts are the print and online publishing activities, as well as all other forms of scientific and science-based forms of communication and exchange undertaken by the consortium and the consortium partners. Other communication instruments for a wider audience will also be used, such as Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn. From the start of the project, media will also be closely involved (through, for instance, radio interviews, newspapers contribution, and TV engagement).

T8.3 Web-platform as a showcase and database for research activities, results and outputs

The consortium will implement an online platform serving a twofold purpose: (1) to become the project's showcase, where all aspects of the research are openly presented, freely accessible and consultable in maximum transparency; (2) to function as the project's link to the official repository of the accumulating data material: research plans, sources, working papers, intermediate reports, scientific and other output.

The project's web-presence will be oriented from the start to attain easy and intuitive transmission of research results, with the description of the project and of its WPs constituting the basic scaffold. To foster

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exchange with the general public, but also with directly concerned partners and with the scientific community, the platform will guarantee an intuitive funneling function leading systematically to each responsible institution, team or even researcher.

All partners of the consortium should also, if feasible, include a portal to LEGITIMULT’s platform on their own websites in order to get greater exposure. This would also help to track where traffic comes from and where it is going.

Figure 2: Summary of the strategy and tasks

3.2 General timeline

The project differentiates between an initial dissemination plan (concentrating on the envisaged goals of the project and its research design), a subsequently updated plan (which will include preliminary findings), and the final dissemination plan (oriented towards the maximum exploitation of our results).

Our strategy and its implementation plan will be updated at each of these stages to ensure it remains accurate. These updates are also important to carry out some specific activities like a precise mapping of our target audience by countries.

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The table of activities and key indicators will be updated every 6 to 8 months, around the following dates whereas the overall strategy will be updated twice during the length of the project:

2023	October 2023: first internal update of the table of activities and key indicators	March 2024: second internal update of the table of activities and key indicators
2024	May 2024: first update of the overall strategy	December 2024: third internal update of the table of activities and key indicators
2025	June 2025: fourth internal update of the table of activities and key indicators	September 2025: final report on dissemination strategy

3.3 Activities and key indicators

Different activities are carried out through each task. These activities are monitored by an indicator. The table below shows the first wave of activities planned from September 2022 to June 2023. This list will be regularly updated and expanded. Most activities are coordinated and carried out by the Institute of Federalism of UNIFR. However, collaboration from each partner is expected.

For the first task, "Partners as multipliers", the main activities are mapping and networking activities. Indeed, for this first period, it is important to identify key stakeholders and interlocutors to the project to raise awareness and engage people. An identification of the dissemination channels of each partner should also be carried out. This can be done on the basis of the proposal, which already lists the most important networks and publications of each partner institution.

In the second task, "Print and online publishing activities", the idea is to focus on the development of our social networks with regular content to be published from January to June 2023. The most important task here is to develop a base. This will also allow us to widely disseminate the first results afterwards.

Finally, for the last task related to the development of the web-platform, the main steps are preparing the content, publishing the website online and developing its role as link to the official repository, Zenodo.

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Activities and indicators: September 2022 to June 2023 (date of first internal update)						
Tasks	Partners	Activities	Time	Indicators	Means verification of	Results 05.25
T8.1 Outreach and involvement of partners functioning as “multipliers”	All	Partners should include a portal to the web-platform on their own websites.	June 2023	At least 5 partners have a portal	Links Traffic indicators from the portal	Eurac Antwerp IDEA Berlin Leiden
	All	Mapping of policy-makers at all levels for each partner	June 2023	List of 10 names per institution	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
	Eurac Research	Promotion of the project within the network: Annual Winter School on Federalism and Governance; ...	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/ policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	Flyers distributed Annual Winter School
		Dissemination of workings papers and policy briefs through relevant communication channels: Blog series: EUreka!; Diversity Governance Papers (DiGoP) - Constitutional, Territorial and Societal Pluralism; ...	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by Eurac Research)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Post on citizens juries Eureka!
Forum of Federations	Mapping of relevant practitioners and academics contacts to the ten partner	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/ policy briefs/any available resources	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and	

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		governments, as well as relevant ministries of beneficiaries' countries		distributed to at least 5 people of the network		will be finalized with the toolbox
		Dissemination on ForFed channels: podcasts; short web blogs; social media (mainly Twitter, Facebook, ...)	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by ForFed)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Regular reposts
	University of Fribourg	Mapping of relevant stakeholders in the network and promotion of the project within the network: IFF Advisory Board of cantonal officials; cantons and CH foundation; Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC) of the Federal Department of Foreign Affairs (FDFA); ...	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/ policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
		Dissemination on relevant channels - Blog series: 50 Shades of Federalism (global audience); IFF Newsletter; webinar series: Turn on Federalism (global audience); ...	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by UNIFR)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Post on the website after each main event

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	University of Bergen	Dissemination on relevant channels: several publications using the Regional Authority Index, the Local Autonomy Index, and other decentralisation indices; several publications on multilevel governance; editor of the book series on Comparative Territorial Politics published by Palgrave Macmillan; ...	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by UiB)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Participation in conferences and articles
	Institute for Ethnic Studies	Mapping of relevant stakeholders of the network and promotion: Academic Network for Cooperation in South East Europe; International Regional Conference; ...	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
		Dissemination on relevant channels: treatises and documents, Journal of Ethnic Studies (TD) / dissemination on relevant channels: Razprave in gradivo (RIG – since 1960); the Etničnost/Ethnicity collection of books/monographs since 1991; IES Newsletter	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by IES)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Participation in conferences and articles
	University of Antwerp	Mapping of relevant stakeholders of the network promotion of the project within the network: Errera Council; Flemish government on external affairs; ...	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox

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		Dissemination on relevant channels: Law and Cosmopolitan Values book series; ICONnect - blog of the International Journal of Constitutional Law; Advisory board of Regional and Federal Studies	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by University of Antwerp)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Participation in conferences and articles
	Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia	Mapping of relevant stakeholders of the network and promotion of the project: "Manuel Giménez Abad" Foundation; Spanish Association of Parliamentary Lawyers; ...	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
		Dissemination on relevant channels: Journal editorship: "Cuadernos Manuel Giménez Abad"	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by UNIFR)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Participation in conferences and articles
	Freie Universität Berlin	Identification of relevant networks, mapping of key stakeholders and promotion of the project	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
	Faculty of Political Science, University of Zagreb	Mapping of relevant stakeholders of the network and promotion of the project: ethnic minorities' NGOs and councils, and representatives of national minorities (at local and regional level)	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox

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		Dissemination on relevant channels: Croatian Political Science Review (SCOPUS and WoS); Forum for Security Studies - annual scientific publication; FPZG web; Facebook; Twitter accounts	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by FPZG)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Participation in conferences and articles
	International IDEA	Mapping of relevant stakeholders of the network and promotion of the project: Engagement in Electoral Law Reform Network; Parliamentary Assistance Networks; Regional Governance Networks	June 2023	Flyer/working papers/policy briefs/any available resources distributed to at least 5 people of the network	List shared with UNIFR	The mapping is in process and will be finalized with the toolbox
		Dissemination on relevant channels: IDEA newsletter; social media accounts; Global State of Democracy report series; podcast; ...	May 2024	1 reference or 1 publication through each relevant channel (to be defined by IDEA)	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	Consistent social media promotion, 1 workshop organized, 1 podcast series ongoing
T8.2 Print and online publishing activities of the consortium partners + other communications	All partners	Press release for the beginning of the project	Until January 2023	2 newspapers presenting the project on a regional and national level for each partner	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI	UNIFR: done
	All partners	Project leaflet translated	June 2023	Leaflet in several languages (at least 3)	Leaflets saved on the drive	Translated in 7 languages
	All partners	Articles in local press about the project written by researchers of LEGITIMULT	Until March 2023	At least 3 articles	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to	1 article, 2 radio interviews

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on instruments					the repository/DOI	
	All partners	Participation in scientific conferences and workshop	Depending on WP calendars	Depending on WP calendars	Title of conferences and content sent to UNIFR/DOI/Link to repository	
	All partners	Writing of scientific articles	Depending on WP calendars	Depending on WP calendar	Title of conferences and content sent to UNIFR/DOI/Link to repository	
	UNIFR	Creation of the Twitter account	September 2022	100 subscribers in March 2023	Twitter analytics	225 followers
	UNIFR	Creation of the Facebook group	December 2022	500 subscribers in June 2023	Facebook analytics	100 followers on Facebook
	UNIFR	Creation of the LinkedIn group	December 2022	200 subscribers in March 2023	LinkedIn analytics	171 followers on LinkedIn
	UNIFR	One post on our social media platforms presenting each of our partners with an explanation of their role	January 2022	On Twitter: 2 to 3 likes, shared at least twice; Facebook: 5 likes, shared at least twice; LinkedIn: 5 likes	Social media analytics	Facebook (1-2 likes per post), LinkedIn (3-8 likes per post) Twitter (2-7 likes per post).

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UNIFR	Presentation of each deliverable on our social media when they are released	At the date of the release of the deliverable	On Twitter: 2 to 3 likes, shared at least twice; Facebook: 5 likes, shared at least twice; LinkedIn: 5 likes -> for the first internal update in June 2023, to be updated for the next one	Social media analytics	Facebook (1-2 likes per post), LinkedIn (3-8 likes per post) Twitter (2-7 likes per post).
UNIFR	Presentation of our researchers through social media with their insight on the project	June 2023	On Twitter: 2 to 3 likes, shared at least twice; Facebook: 5 likes, shared at least twice; LinkedIn: 5 likes -> for the first internal update in June 2023, to be updated for the next one	Social media analytics	Campaign still ongoing
UNIFR	Networking and monitoring work of similar projects or topics related to LEGITIMULT to share on our social media	June 2023	At least 5 posts on similar topics and increase of followers thanks to these posts	Post saved and analytics	
UNIFR	Preparation of material for external audience: 1 video of 1-2 minutes presenting the project	February 2023	At least 100 views in June 2023	Social media analytics	800 views on Facebook/Twitter
UNIFR	Calendar of posts and ideas of posts to prepare	December			

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			2023			
	UNIFR	Newsletters about the project	June 2023	2 newsletters shared to 50 subscribers	MailChimp analytics	50 for the first newsletter and 85 for the second
T8.3 Web-platform	UNIFR	Website online	December 2022	100 visits on the website per week until June 2023	WordPress analytics	100 views per month

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3.4 Steps to update the strategy

This strategy will be updated in June 2023 internally by the Institute of Federalism of UNIFR. The following points will be checked:

June 2023 Internal update	Evaluation of the results of the activities and their relevance: evaluation of the use of the hashtags of the project and update if necessary, evaluation of the number of readers of the newsletter and update of the format.
	Choice of new activities and reorientation of activities deemed irrelevant or ineffective: activities like infographics to summarise the project main findings should be organised, their content defined, etc.
	Update of indicators: new indicators have to be prepared according to the advancement of the project. For example, the audience of academic articles, the number of conferences attended by partners, but also how many reviews of articles/books of the project are made and what opinions on it have been shared.
May 2023 Evaluation of the overall strategy	Evaluation of results against targets by audience.
	Evaluation of activities and indicators.
	Evaluation of compliance with different communication and dissemination principles, including the gender perspective.
	Based on the results and findings of the project, key messages will be prepared for each group of audiences and their subcategories.
	Channels may be changed if they are not efficient enough – new channels can be added (Instagram?).
	Evaluation of the participation of partners in the communication process.
	Collection of feedbacks by citizens, stakeholders and consortium members.
	Collection of impact stories to be defined as an objective
	Update of activities and indicators according to the results of the evaluation.
	A new communication and dissemination plan will be prepared (one page, including only the basics).
	Deepening the involvement of key stakeholders.
Next steps for the final evaluation of the strategy to be prepared.	

3.5 Summary of the result of the internal and overall evaluation

We are gradually building up our overall audience, but communication needs to increase with the number of results from the midterm conference onwards. The gender perspective is mostly addressed through images (website) but will be further developed through feedback and reports for the citizens juries. No new social media channels will be added but we need to develop a more specific strategy for each, and not always repost the same content.

Partners do participate in the dissemination and communication process through videos, posts, and reposts. IDEA and Eurac are particularly involved and the coordination should be increased for the last year of the project. A common communication and dissemination plan is shared online with them in order to better share the task.

Some indicators (e.g. Facebook reach) were too unrealistic from the outset, and have since been adapted. A slow but steady increase is now expected.

Dissemination is well on track, but *communication* needs to improve. New activities have to be organized to ensure that relevant stakeholders are targeted and that the project engages in real dialogue with them.

Some analytics

Newsletter: 3 newsletters sent

- MailChimp: 48 recipients for the first one, 83 and 86
- LinkedIn: 53 (first newsletter sent in January 2024)

Web platform: 1,5 k visitors for 2023

WEBINAR: online webinar with around 70 participants. "LEGITIMULT: Legitimate crisis management for the future"

PODCAST: by International IDEA. It is the first of a three-episode series featuring LEGITIMULT, its findings and tools for addressing and solving future crises. 53 downloads the first 7 days, total of 97 since October

A manual assessment of our Twitter followers puts the number of experts/policy makers at around 20 out of 230 subscribers. This does not, of course, reflect the audience for posts, which may exceed the number of followers. International IDEA's reposts, for example, reach a much wider audience.

*How to improve our reach (in **bold** are priorities):*

- **Increase the number of posts /**
- **Have more activities besides social media: organize another workshop for communication.**
- **Explore the possibility of using targeted advertisements to widen the reach of our posts.**
- Once the first results are published, increase the networking efforts with our sister projects REGROUP and ROBUST.
- Include LEGITIMULT website in more posts, ask International IDEA, the Forum of Federations and EURAC with priority to have at least one post per month on the website, as they have a very good outreach. We will also ascertain whether other institutions would agree to publish more.
- **Edit and publish more videos.**
- Press upon partners to like and share our posts: posts of individuals get more likes, more interactions, more comments as compared to "institutional" accounts. We will try to encourage the people involved (especially those who do not have an exclusively private account) to also post more themselves.
- Press upon partners to make a list of key stakeholders and send the flyer presenting the project when relevant. Ask for another list of key stakeholders once we have our first results.
- **Use short moving graphics/videos instead of static images.**
- **Work on more qualitative and in-depth content with International IDEA (e.g. longer written interviews).**

IV. Communication toolbox

The communication toolbox provides elements for the visual identity of the project. LEGITIMULT will create and make use of various communication channels/tools, which will be both online and offline, as well as interactive (face-to-face), to achieve an efficient and effective interaction with the different stakeholders. Templates of the most common documents used by partners are also presented here and will be at the disposal of each partner on the shared drive of the project.

More explanations on how to use fonts, logos and colours will be available on the shared drive (MS Teams Folder): [WP 8 - COMMUNICATION](#)

4.1 Logo

The LEGITIMULT project logo is presented below. It has to be included in all the project dissemination material, documents, and communication tools throughout the lifetime of the project. Its purpose is to **brand** our project as much as possible in order to be recognizable.

The logo is available in various formats each of them serving a different purpose (for printing or online activities). The logo exists in extended version and in a compact version. It is also available in colours and in greyscales.

The extended version should be used in priority. When impossible (because of the background, or when there not enough space), then the compact version can be displayed. For social media, the compact version serves as a picture profile and the extended one to display the full title of the project. On a white background, logos with a white or transparent background can be used. The coloured background is mostly used for the website.

The logo represents the idea of multilevel governance through three imaginary regions linked to one another. The regions are also slightly overlapping in order to represent their interdependence.

Figure 3: Compact versions of the logo

Figure 4: Extended versions of the logo

4.2 Fonts

Before using any templates, please activate the following fonts on Adobe or contact legitimult@unifr.ch:

Font *DIN CONDENSED BOLD*

<https://fonts.adobe.com/fonts/din-condensed>

Font *SOURCE SANS, REGULAR*

<https://fonts.adobe.com/fonts/source-sans>

These two fonts are mainly used for titles. *Calibri (body)* can be used for the text.

DIN CONDENSED,BOLD

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

SOURCE SANS VARIABLE, REGULAR

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

4.3 Colours

The various document templates provide the following colors.

4.4 Website

The LEGITIMULT website is currently being designed and will go live at the end of 2022. It will be based on the project's graphic charter.

The website aims to present the project and its main objectives, its partners and collaborators (menu "About us").

Each work package and area of research will be presented individually (menu "Research"). These presentations will be accessible, even to non-specialists. A colourful and user-oriented interface is thus favoured. The directly accessible content has been simplified as much as possible. However, the more complex information required by specialists or people who want to know more is also available to download.

Events and news of the project will be accessible through the menu "News & Events". Media coverage will also be displayed in this menu.

The site will also offer all publications for download from the official repository, those created by the project (policy briefs and working papers), but will also serve as a reference base for all articles, books and data generated by the project. The menu "Output" will present our results and findings while the menu "Data" will reference all data produced by the project (qualitative and quantitative).

The website will be regularly updated and enriched. A first evaluation of its contents and use will be conducted internally in June 2023.

Figure 5: Menu layout

4.5 Social media

The same content will be posted on each of our social networks, namely Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn (subject to evaluation). However, due to the specificities of each audience, some adaptations will be made.

Twitter is used by most of LEGITIMULT's partner institutions. The official accounts of politicians and important target people allow for an outreach towards interesting discussions. The network is also used extensively by researchers. The aim is to publish tweets and Twitter feeds, with strong background information that is attractive to this audience. Links to partners websites or social media is also really important to strengthen the dissemination of the content.

Facebook is very much used by the general public, but the average age of its users is relatively high. Our Facebook group aims to reach a wider audience. Thus, the use of videos, images and drawings will be favoured. The possibility to create events for online courses and conferences will be used.

Finally, LinkedIn is a professional network. This platform will be used to highlight the results, conferences and researchers of the LEGITIMULT network.

4.6 Templates

In order to ensure that the visual identity and the **branding** of the LEGITIMULT project is clearly recognizable, different models are being prepared. Each of these templates serves a particular purpose and the design is adapted accordingly.

a. Project leaflet

The project booklet is built on a similar model for all partners. A copy in English is available for each organisation. A template version is also available (InDesign format) to be adapted by the communication officers with translations into the different languages of the project.

b. Covers for social media platforms

Three social networks will be used by LEGITIMULT: Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn. They are the three main social media used mostly by partners. Names of researchers, name of their institutions and their accounts on social media have been collected in order to facilitate a good dissemination through direct tagging (with their agreement).

Some hashtags used for the LEGITIMULT project include: #LEGITIMULT; #covidcrisis; #governance; #legitimacy; #HEU, #HorizonEurope

These hashtags are key to control the discussions and the feed of conversations regarding the project. They will also be evaluated during the first internal update.

Initially, each one will have the same following cover, with the title of the project in full:

Figure 6: Profile picture

Figure 7: Banner for social media

As the strategy is updated internally, different covers can be created, always respecting the graphic charter.

Social networks will be mainly managed by UNIFR. Each partner is required to share important information with the UNIFR and its Institute of Federalism communication officer.

c. PowerPoint presentations

LEGITIMULT will be presented in several events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. A presentation template (PPT) has been designed in line with LEGITIMULT graphic identity. Each partner is required to use the same PPT template when giving conferences about findings of the project.

The template is available in the common drive: [3 TEMPLATES](#)

d. LEGITIMULT official deliverable template

LEGITIMULT's deliverable template was produced in line with the general graphic identity for all communication and dissemination materials and will be used by the consortium partners for all official deliverable to be send to the European Union.

The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title), as well as the authors' information.

Figure 8: LEGITIMULT deliverable template (cover)

e. Working and policy papers

Two types of publications will be created for and by the project:

- Working papers are documents presenting the research, methodological discussions and first results. The aim is to provide, in an open science context, documents that allow to follow the progress of LEGITIMULT.
- Policy briefs are documents for policy-makers, managers and decision-makers at all levels of government. These documents focus on a specific theme or question that practitioners may have and attempt to provide an answer based on the project's results.

These two types of publication will be identifiable by two easily identifiable covers. They will be available to download on the project website through a link to their official repository, **Zenodo**.

f. Newsletter

A newsletter presenting the project's results will be published every two to three months. An internal evaluation will be carried out in June 2023. Subscription to the newsletter will be done through the LEGITIMULT website via **Mailchimp**. Its objective is to present the progress and current issues related to the project, and to introduce the members of the consortium.

4.7 Content of the shared drive

Documents > General > **WP 8 - COMMUNICATION**

Name	Modified
1. VISUAL IDENTITY	November 7
2. PRESS	November 7
3. PICTURES	November 7
4_WEBSITE	November 7
Communication_contacts_details.xlsx	6 days ago

Figure 9: Content of the common drive

The shared drive provides access to all communication tools of the project. It is the complete "toolbox" for the partners and their communication managers.

The "Visual identity" folder contains the project's logos and those of the partners, as well as the mandatory references, templates and elements of the graphic charter. Indications on how to use fonts, colours and logos will also be displayed.

The "Press" folder collects all media contributions about LEGITIMULT. Press release templates are also available.

The "Pictures" folder collects all pictures of the project, the consortium members, and the events that can be used by the partners for communication purposes.

Finally, the "Website" folder contains all the written elements of the website.

The Excel file "Communication details" identifies the people in charge of communication and collects all the names of the institutions for the social networks in order to write the most targeted posts possible.

Other files will undoubtedly be added as and when needed and whenever the strategy is updated.

V. Update of the indicators – May 2024 to September 2025

Activities and indicators: May 2024 to Sept 2025				
Tasks	Partners	Activities	Indicators	Means of verification
T8.1 Outreach and involvement of partners functioning as “multipliers”	All Partners from WP 7	Mapping of relevant stakeholders for disseminating the toolbox	Mapping shared with WP 7	Documents
	All	Partners should publish news about the project on their own social media	Each LEGITIMULT post is shared by at least 1 person from the network	Links Post saved and their reach as well (number of likes etc.)
T8.2 Print and online publishing activities of the consortium partners + other communication instruments	All partners	Project leaflet distributed	Leaflet distributed during events/conferences/etc by partners: at least by 3 partners before the end of the project	Number of leaflets distributed by partners
	All partners	Articles in local press about the project written by researchers of LEGITIMULT	At least 3 articles in newspaper before Sept 25	Posts and articles saved with UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI
	All partners	Participation in scientific conferences and workshops	Depending on WP calendars	Title of conferences and content sent to UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI
	All partners	Writing of scientific articles	Depending on WP calendar	Title of conferences and content sent to UNIFR/links to the repository/DOI
	UNIFR	Creation of the Twitter account: paid and unpaid, check if feasible / wait if LinkedIn posts work	300 subscribers by Sept 25	Twitter analytics
	UNIFR	Advertisement on Facebook: paid and unpaid	150 subscribers by Sept 25	Facebook analytics
	UNIFR	Creation of the LinkedIn group: pay for a post and see if we increase our audience	200 subscribers by Sept 25	LinkedIn analytics
	UNIFR	Networking and monitoring work of similar projects or topics related to LEGITIMULT to share on our social media	Reshare at least 3 posts on similar topics and monthly increase of followers thanks to these posts	Posts saved and analytics

	UNIFR International IDEA Forum of Federations Eurac	At least one more online webinar and 2 additional podcasts	at least 100 views/participants or listeners	Posts saved and analytics
	UNIFR International IDEA Forum of Federations Eurac	New in-depth posts or news to share with more content than regular posts	100 views for each in-depth post	Posts saved and analytics
	UNIFR	Post at least 10 more videos on all social media	100 views on each social media platform	Social media analytics
	UNIFR	2 to 3 animated posts about the last deliverables (methodology) /mid-term conference	On Twitter: 2 to 3 likes, shared at least twice	Social media analytics
			On Facebook: 5 likes, shared at least twice	
			LinkedIn: 5 likes	
	UNIFR International IDEA Forum of Federations Eurac	Calendar of posts and ideas of posts to prepare	News calendar to prepare together with International IDEA, Forum of Federations and Eurac	Document online in the shared drive
	UNIFR	Newsletters about the project	3 more newsletter shared with 100 people with MailChimp and LinkedIn	MailChimp analytics and LinkedIn
T8.3 Web-platform	UNIFR	Website online: publish results and advertise to increase our website audience	From 80 to 200 views per month; reach 200 at least once.	WordPress analytics